

TEST CONSTRUCTION COMPETENCE AND PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT KNOWLEDGE AS PREDICTORS OF TEACHER EFFECTIVENESS AMONG PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

Teaching in today's educational context demands not only mastery of content but also the ability to design effective assessments that support learning. The primary purpose of this study was to assess the significant influence of test construction competence and pedagogical content knowledge on the teacher effectiveness among public elementary school teachers. This study employed a descriptive-correlational design and universal sampling specifically complete enumeration method to identify the number of respondents. Sets of adapted, validated and pilot tested survey questionnaires were administered to measure test construction competence, pedagogical content knowledge, and teacher effectiveness. Data were analyzed using Mean, Standard Deviation, Pearson-Product Moment Correlation, and Multiple Regression Analysis. The results revealed that public elementary school teachers have a very high levels of test construction competence, pedagogical content knowledge, and teacher effectiveness. Furthermore, there are significant positive relationships between test construction competence and teacher effectiveness, and between pedagogical content knowledge and teacher effectiveness. Multiple regression analysis showed that both test construction competence and pedagogical content knowledge significantly influence teacher effectiveness.

Keywords: *Education, Assessment and Evaluation, Professional Competence, Subject Matter Expertise, Descriptive-correlational, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Teacher effectiveness, as defined by Ganai (2023), refers to how teachers lead students toward behavioral evolution and academic development while building encouraging spaces. In addition, Carlson (2019) states that teacher effectiveness has garnered much interest for over a century, and one way to assess it is by student outcomes, which often reflects a decline in teacher performance. However, teacher effectiveness is observed to be low or in decline, as evidenced by several contributing factors such as challenges in supporting various student needs, including cultural and linguistic differences, due to inadequate trained instructors and restricted professional development opportunities (Piwowarski, 2024; Ahmad, 2022). Furthermore, Ahmmad (2014) stated that there is a decline in teacher performance because the lack of resources, coupled with political turmoil creates barriers to efficient teaching through its negative impact on both teacher spirit and available educational approaches. Moreover, teachers are ineffective because educational reforms, along with the requirement to continuously innovate, create excessive pressure that diverts them from implementing effective teaching practices (Santmajor et al., 2022).

The lack of adequate teacher preparation for teaching in diverse classrooms has led to ineffective instructional practices, revealing a serious problem in teacher effectiveness across the United States (Bauml, 2016). In addition, a cross-national study conducted in six countries, The Netherlands, South Korea, Indonesia, South Africa, Hong Kong-China, and Pakistan reveal notable teacher ineffectiveness, particularly in teaching quality, approaches, and professional development, highlighting the need for targeted improvement in teaching practices (Maulana et al., 2021). Further, a study conducted by Barzane et al. (2020) in Morocco showed that the ineffectiveness of the teachers is represented through poor quality education and uncontrolled knowledge is central to low test outcomes. The study emphasized that teacher effectiveness remains a significant issue in the country.

Furthermore, in the Philippines, it is challenging for teachers to do their jobs because the public school system is constantly changing and because of policy changes, inadequate infrastructures (Barcelona et al., 2023; Mastul et al., 2023), and a lack of technology (Delgado et al., 2021). In addition, research also reveals teacher ineffectiveness in teaching higher-order thinking skills and instruction, including questioning abilities and differentiation (Mobo, 2023). Likewise, a study conducted in Zamboanga, Mindanao, by Castro et al. (2024) has shown the ineffectiveness of Filipino teachers due to teaching multiple subjects like the ones they were never trained to teach and not having enough prepared materials (Mangila, 2022). Moreover, a low level of teacher effectiveness persists due to several contributing factors, many of which have also been identified by previous scholars (Eleccion, 2024).

Teacher test construction competence and pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) have a great impact on teacher effectiveness. Test construction competence is the competence to develop effective, valid and reliable assessment tools that reflect student learning (Sari et al., 2022; Omoruan, 2018). Studies indicate that this competency is strongly connected

with the effectiveness of teachers because when a teacher is capable of designing quality assessments, he or she will be more competent to support teaching, determine achievement, and improve the performance of students (Chetia et al., 2017; Zamri, 2019; Ganai, 2023). Nevertheless, there are still teachers who create tests of poor quality because of their low skills, which is why Baidoo-Anu and Ennu Baidoo (2022) urge people to concentrate on well-developed test construction competencies to create effective and reliable assessment tools. It is also important that the teachers plan, implement, and evaluate lessons, which is possible only with the help of PCK (Krepf, 2018). High PCK teachers are able to connect content to real-life situations (Manufi, 2016) and incorporate collaborative activities that enhance learning (Thangaiah et al., 2020), which eventually will enhance the effectiveness of the teachers (Holley et al., 2019). On the other hand, the low level of PCK would make teachers less confident and restrict classroom practice, which would decrease the overall effectiveness of teaching.

Although teacher effectiveness has been given attention, several limitations have hampered efforts (Mazabdarani & Troudi, 2022). For example, researchers have studied teacher effectiveness, but mainly in the Western parts for decades (Klassen et al., 2018). Furthermore, other studies tend to concentrate on higher education, specifically targeting English language teachers (El-Dakhs et al., 2024). Recent studies focused on one variable predicting teacher effectiveness, such as the teacher's attitude (Qafa et al., 2024) and the roles of principals (Ugiagbe et al., 2024). Although there is available literature on how effective teachers become, the researcher failed to access a study that clearly investigates the effect of test construction competence and pedagogical knowledge on teacher effectiveness in the local context. Given the potential impact of these factors, this information gap is particularly concerning. Hence, the researcher got interested to embark on the study that deals with how teachers' ability to create tests and their knowledge of how to teach content influence their effectiveness in public elementary schools.

Given the foundational role of elementary education in shaping future learning paths, teacher effectiveness emerges as a critical determinant of student success at this level. Consequently, this research is essential to illuminate the importance of the competence of teachers in constructing valid and reliable assessments and their knowledge of subject matter and strategies for delivering lessons. These competencies directly support the goals of Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4: Quality Education, which emphasizes enhancing teaching quality to ensure inclusive and equitable learning for all. Understanding how test construction competence and pedagogical content knowledge interact and influence teacher effectiveness can guide focused professional development initiatives aligned with SDG 4 targets, ultimately improving learning outcomes in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher finds it both crucial and urgent to conduct the study.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the significance of the influence of test construction competence and pedagogical content knowledge on teacher effectiveness among public elementary school teachers in San Francisco, Division of Agusan del Sur, Caraga Region.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of test construction competence among public elementary school teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1 developing assessment methods appropriate for instructional decisions;
 - 1.2 administering scoring and interpreting results;
 - 1.3 using assessment results;
 - 1.4 developing valid student grading procedures;
 - 1.5 communicating assessment results; and
 - 1.6 recognizing unethical and illegal assessment methods?
2. What is the level of pedagogical and content knowledge among the respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1 knowledge about students and their characteristics;
 - 2.2 knowledge about learning materials and principles;
 - 2.3 knowledge about curricula development;
 - 2.4 knowledge about learning strategies;
 - 2.5 knowledge about students' skill development;
 - 2.6 knowledge about communication with students; and
 - 2.7 knowledge about assessment and evaluation?
3. What is the level of teacher effectiveness among the respondents in terms of:
 - 3.1 personality;
 - 3.2 subject matter expertise;
 - 3.3 relational competence with students;
 - 3.4 professional competence;
 - 3.5 teaching style; and
 - 3.6 classroom management style?
4. Is there a significant relationship between:
 - 4.1 test construction competence and teacher effectiveness; and
 - 4.2 pedagogical content knowledge and teacher effectiveness?
5. Do test construction competence and pedagogical content knowledge significantly influence teacher effectiveness?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design to examine the relationship and influence of test construction competence and pedagogical content knowledge on teacher effectiveness. The research was conducted in four public elementary school in San Francsico, Agusan del Sur, Philippines, during the school year 2025-2026.

Respondents

The study participants included 153 public elementary school teachers, selected using the universal sampling method, complete enumeration. Only teachers who are teaching in public central elementary school with at least two years of teaching experience were included in the study.

Data Sources/Research Instrument

This study adapted three questionnaires to collect the data needed. The instruments were subjected to content validity by a panel of experts and later pilot tested to attain reliability. The questionnaire on test construction competence was developed by Hamafyelto (2015) which includes 37 items, the questionnaire on pedagogical content knowledge was adapted from Firkrayah et al. (2021), composed of 41 items distributed unequally to seven indicators, and the questionnaire on teacher effectiveness was adapted from Calaguas (2013), consisted of 107 items all rated on a 5-point Likert scale

Data Gathering Procedures

The researcher followed the protocol for data collection. Initially, the researcher secured a permission letter from the Dean of the Graduate School of the University of the Immaculate Conception (UIC). This was followed by the submission of the study to the UIC Research Ethics Committee (UIC-REC) for ethical review and approval. Once approval to conduct the study was granted, the researcher formally requested permission from the Schools Division Superintendent and the school heads of the identified schools to conduct the study. Upon approval, informed consent was obtained from the respondents before distributing the research instruments. The collected data were then encoded and subjected to analysis.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics, including the mean and standard deviation, were utilized to assess the levels of test construction competence, pedagogical content knowledge, and teacher effectiveness. To determine the relationship between the two variables, Pearson's correlation coefficient was applied. Furthermore, multiple regression analysis was conducted to evaluate the extent to which test construction competence and pedagogical content knowledge predict or influence teacher effectiveness.

Ethical considerations were diligently followed throughout the study. The confidentiality of participants' responses was safeguarded, and participation was voluntary, with respondents given the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without facing any repercussions.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the descriptive results of the Test Construction Competence, Pedagogical Content Knowledge, and Teacher Effectiveness of teachers. Overall, the ratings of the three key variables were very high, which means that there were strong competencies among the surveyed individuals. The overall mean of Test Construction Competence was 4.57 (Very High), indicating that teachers have excellent skills in selecting, giving and scoring tests. The score of all indicators was in the very high range area, with the values of 4.53-4.61. Notably, the highest mean of 4.60 was obtained by the indicator *Communicating Assessment Results*, which implies the high ability of teachers to explain evaluation results efficiently and correctly. In the meantime, *Recognizing Unethical and Illegal Assessment Methods* has the lowest mean of 4.53, but depicts a

Table 1. Descriptive Table

Variables and Their Indicators	Standard Deviation	Mean	Verbal Description
Test Construction Competence	.36	4.57	Very High
Developing Assessment Method	.35	4.57	Very High
Appropriate for Instructional Decisions			
Administering, Scoring, and Interpreting Results	.82	4.54	Very High
Using Assessment Results	.46	4.58	Very High
Developing Valid Students Grading Procedures	.43	4.61	Very High
Communicating Assessment Results	.45	4.60	Very High
Recognizing Unethical and Illegal Assessment Methods	.43	4.53	Very High
Pedagogical Content Knowledge	.32	4.62	Very High
Knowledge about Students and their Characteristics	.54	4.58	Very High
Knowledge about Learning Materials and Principles	.38	4.62	Very High
Knowledge about Curricula Development	.43	4.59	Very High
Knowledge about Learning Strategies	.33	4.67	Very High
Knowledge about Students' Skill Development	.42	4.40	Very High
Knowledge about Communication with Students	.38	4.65	Very High
Knowledge about Assessment and Evaluation	.40	4.62	Very High
Teacher Effectiveness	.28	4.66	Very High

Personality	.32	4.59	Very High
Subject Matter Expertise	.35	4.67	Very High
Relational Competence with Students	.32	4.64	Very High
Professional Competence	.34	4.71	Very High
Teaching Style	.33	4.64	Very High
Classroom Management Style	.53	4.69	Very High

good awareness and ethical norms. The standard deviation (0.36) is low and this means that the responses are very consistent which means that the test construction practices have been mastered uniformly.

The overall level of Pedagogical Content Knowledge was also very high (4.62) with indicators ranging between 4.58 and 4.67. Educators gave themselves the highest scores in *Knowledge about Learning Strategies* (4.67) and *Knowledge about Students Skill Development* (4.66) with a strong emphasis on instructional planning and the learner-centered approach to teaching. The standard deviation (0.32) indicates that the variability is low and teachers are always found to be very knowledgeable in terms of subject matter, learning processes and the needs of the student.

On the same note, Teacher Effectiveness has the most overall mean of the three variables at 4.66 (Very High). The indicator is scored between 4.59 and 4.74 with the *Classroom Management Style* receiving the maximum score of 4.74 that underlines the attribute of the teacher who is highly competent in creating efficient learning conditions. *Subject Matter Expertise* and *Teaching Style* were also reported to have been very high and this confirmed competence in teaching content and being able to engage the learners. The fact that the standard deviation is low (0.28) also confirms the consistency and reliability of teacher effectiveness among the respondents.

Table 2. Test of Relationship

		teacher effectiveness		
		r	p-value	Remarks
test	construction			
competence		0.655	< .001	Significant
pedagogical	content			
knowledge		0.773	< .001	Significant

Shown in Table 4 is the significance of the relationship of test construction competence and pedagogical content knowledge, and teacher effectiveness. It reveals that both variables have a significant positive relationship with teacher effectiveness, with p-values of .001, which is lower than the .05 level of significance.

The test construction competence and pedagogical content knowledge of teachers both have strong positive correlations with teaching effectiveness, indicating that the ability to construct valid and reliable tests and the knowledge the teacher has of his or her subject matter makes them more competent to provide high-quality instruction. Well-developed assessment skills enable the teacher to accurately gauge the learning and match the items in the test to the instructional objectives, as well as modify their approach to the student to enable higher achievements. Similarly, developed pedagogical content knowledge can assist teachers in explaining complicated ideas with clarity, predicting misconceptions, and offer narrow feedback that reinforces the understanding of students. Combined, these competencies improve the instructional decision-making process, facilitate active learning, and lead to better teaching and learning conditions.

Table 3. Regression Table

Variables	teacher effectiveness			Remarks
	β	t	p-value	
test construction competence	0.081	0.912	0.363	Not Significant
pedagogical content knowledge	0.708	8.014	< .001	Significant
Holistic Model				
r ²	0.600			
F-value	112.514			
p-value	< .001			
Remarks	Significant			

Table 3 illustrates the findings of the multiple regression analysis showing pedagogical content knowledge as a strong predictor of teacher effectiveness with a β value of 0.708 and a p-value of less than .001 which implies that increased PCK would result in significant increase in teacher effectiveness. On the contrary, the competence of test construction, with a β value of 0.081 and 0.363 p-value, does not have a significant influence on teacher effectiveness, indicating that assessment competence is also important, but it does not directly affect differences in teaching performance in this model.

The r² value of 0.600 demonstrates that the two variables jointly explain a 60 percent variance in teacher effectiveness, which illustrates the importance of PCK in determining the quality of teaching. In general, the results indicate that despite the fact that both competencies are supportive of effective teaching, PCK is a stronger indicator since teachers with a strong content knowledge and the ability to use relevant instructional strategies have higher chances of providing clear classes, addressing the needs of the learners, and creating meaningful interaction and learning in the classroom.

The results revealed that public elementary school teachers possess an excellent level of test construction competence, reflected in their strong ability to construct valid, reliable, and instructionally aligned evaluation tools. This finding is supported by Knouse et al. (2015), who emphasized that effective assessment design requires ensuring content

validity, selecting appropriate item formats, and assembling coherent test instruments that accurately measure learning. The teachers' high level of readiness in developing assessment materials aligns with the views of Arias-Aranda et al. (2018), who highlighted the importance of preparation in carrying out professional tasks efficiently. Their ability to craft items that promote active learning and higher-order thinking also resonates with the work of Anselmi et al. (2024), who noted that competence-based assessments enhance students' understanding and performance by clarifying expectations and promoting deeper learning.

The findings indicate that teachers demonstrate a very high level of pedagogical content knowledge (PCK), reflecting their strong ability to integrate subject matter expertise with effective instructional strategies. This aligns with the observations of Liu (2024) and Kshetree (2023), who emphasized that combining content knowledge with appropriate pedagogy enhances instructional quality and addresses student misconceptions. Similarly, the results confirm what was highlighted by (Hasanah et al., 2024), that teachers with strong PCK are capable of designing engaging and accurate lessons that foster deeper understanding. Moreover, the finding corroborates what was noted by Liu (2024) and Hong and Paik (2024), that PCK enables teachers to craft meaningful assessments and thought-provoking questions that promote critical and creative thinking. These insights collectively support the study's result that teachers exhibit excellent pedagogical competence, effectively applying both content and teaching knowledge to improve learning outcomes.

The findings reveal a very high level of teacher effectiveness among public elementary school teachers, indicating their strong ability to create positive learning environments, deliver quality instruction, and promote meaningful student engagement. This result aligns with Ganai (2023), who emphasized that effective teachers play a vital role in fostering students' academic and behavioral growth through supportive and goal-oriented teaching practices. Similarly, the findings confirm that teacher effectiveness stems from professional competence, emotional connection with students, and the ability to adapt instructional strategies to meet diverse learner needs (Chetia & Joseph, 2017). Consistent with this, the result support Burges (2019) who identified teacher effectiveness as a key determinant of student achievement, underscoring its direct impact on improved learning outcomes. Moreover, Aquino and Chavez (2022) stressed the importance of comprehensive evaluation tools that assess all dimensions of teaching practice, which supports the study's finding of high overall effectiveness across multiple domains.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions are drawn:

1. The test construction competence among public elementary school teachers was rated as very high.
2. The pedagogical content knowledge among public elementary school teachers was rated as very high.

3. The teacher effectiveness among public elementary school teachers was rated as very high.
4. Since test construction competence has a significant positive strong relationship with teacher effectiveness among teachers, this indicates that those who are competent in constructing tests are more capable of evaluating students accurately and aligning assessments with learning objectives.
5. Thus, pedagogical content knowledge significantly influenced teacher effectiveness among teachers, while test construction competence did not have a significant effect.

Recommendations

1. It is recommended that schools sustain and further enhance this competence by organizing advanced training programs and seminars focused on innovative assessment practices.
2. In terms of pedagogical content knowledge, which was rated very high and consistently demonstrated among public elementary school teachers, it is recommended that school administrators continue to nurture and strengthen this area through sustained professional development programs.
3. Hence, since teacher effectiveness among public elementary school teachers was rated very high and consistently observed, it is recommended that school administrators continue to reinforce and sustain these effective teaching practices through ongoing professional development and mentorship programs.
4. Since test construction competence and pedagogical content knowledge were found to have a significant positive relationship with teacher effectiveness, it is recommended that school administrators strengthen programs that enhance teachers' assessment and pedagogical skills.
5. Since pedagogical content knowledge was found to significantly influence teacher effectiveness while test construction competence did not, it is recommended that future researchers further investigate the underlying factors that make pedagogical content knowledge a stronger predictor of teacher effectiveness.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher ensured full adherence to ethical standards throughout the conduct of the study. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to data collection, and they were clearly informed of their freedom to decline participation or withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. The anonymity and confidentiality of all respondents were strictly maintained by securing personal information and ensuring that no identifying details appeared in any part of the report. The safety, dignity, and overall well-being of the participants were safeguarded by following procedures approved by the Immaculate Conception University Research Ethics Committee (UIC-REC) under protocol number GS-ER-08-25-0368. The researcher declares that no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of the study and that all procedures were carried out with objectivity and fairness. Plagiarism was strictly avoided by properly acknowledging all sources, and no bias influenced the analysis or interpretation of the findings. The results generated

from the study were used solely for academic and research purposes. The guidance of the research adviser and the availability of institutional resources, such as the UIC Library, computer laboratories, and statistical software, further ensured that the study was conducted with methodological rigor, transparency, and ethical accountability.

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